

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature and Culture Research

كتاب المتون الكاملة للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية

Editörler - المحررون - Editors

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04-08 Kasım/November 2025 - Antalya/Türkiye

ISBN: 978-625-92747-0-6

Yayımlanma Tarihi (Publishing Date): 30.11.2025

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Kapak Resmi:

KÜTÜPHANE BİLGİ KARTI

1. Basım, Elektronik Kitap (Çevrim içi / Web tabanlı)

210 x 297 mm

Kaynakça var, dizin yok.

ISBN 978-625-92747-0-6

1. Dil Bilimi 2. Edebiyat 3. Kültür Araştırmaları

PDF yayın

Yayımlanma adresi: <https://saybildercongress.com/dekak/>

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ÖN SÖZ

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 04–08 Kasım 2025 tarihleri arasında Türkiye'nin Antalya kentinde gerçekleştirilmiş; dil, edebiyat ve kültür alanlarını disiplinlerarası bir bakış açısıyla ele alan önemli bir bilimsel buluşma platformu olmuştur. Kongre, Saybiller Topluluğu organizasyonunda; başta Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage University (Tunus) olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının akademik desteğiyle düzenlenmiştir.

Kongre kapsamında, farklı akademik gelenekleri ve araştırma perspektiflerini temsil eden 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı bilim insanlarıyla buluşturulmuştur. Ayrıca Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça dillerinde yapılan çağrılarla geniş bir uluslararası katılım sağlanmıştır. Bu çok dilli ve kapsayıcı çağrı süreci sonucunda gönderilen bildirimler, bilimsel etik ve kalite ilkeleri doğrultusunda hakem değerlendirme sürecinden geçirilmiştir. Yapılan değerlendirmeler neticesinde Türkiye'den 34, Türkiye dışından ise Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Katar, Kuveyt, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı ve Ürdün olmak üzere 13 farklı ülkeden 114 bildiri, kongre programında yer almış; böylece toplam 148 bildiri bilim dünyasıyla paylaşılmıştır.

Bu kongre kitabında yer alan çalışmalar; dil, edebiyat ve kültür araştırmalarında güncel kuramsal yaklaşımları, özgün analizleri ve farklı coğrafyalardan gelen akademik deneyimleri bir araya getirmektedir. Kongre süreci, özellikle uluslararası ve kültürlerarası iş birliğine dayalı araştırmaların bilimsel bilginin evrenselleşmesi ve akademik etkileşimin sürdürülebilirliği açısından taşıdığı önemi bir kez daha ortaya koymuştur.

Bu bağlamda araştırmacıların; disiplinlerarası çalışmalara daha fazla yönelmeleri, ortak projeler ve çok yazarlı uluslararası yayınlar aracılığıyla akademik etkileşimi güçlendirmeleri ve farklı dillerde bilimsel üretim yaparak çalışmalarının görünürlüğünü artırmaları önem arz etmektedir. Üniversitelerin, araştırma merkezlerinin ve diğer paydaşların ise genç araştırmacıları destekleyen, uluslararası akademik ağları teşvik eden ve nitelikli bilimsel üretimi sürdürülebilir kılan yapılar oluşturmaya devam etmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu kongrenin ve elinizdeki kitabın; alan yazınına anlamlı katkılar sunmasını, yeni akademik iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamasını ve dil, edebiyat ile kültür araştırmalarında nitelikli bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmesini temenni eder; kongrenin gerçekleştirilmesinde emeği geçen tüm kurumlara, hakemlere, davetli konuşmacılara ve değerli araştırmacılara teşekkür ederiz.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

PREFACE

The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research, held in Antalya, Türkiye, between November 4–8, 2025, constituted a significant academic platform that brought together studies in language, literature, and culture within an interdisciplinary framework. The congress was organized by the Saybilder Community, with the academic support of several higher education institutions, most notably Mardin Artuklu University and Carthage University.

Within the scope of the congress, invited speakers from six different countries met with scholars representing diverse academic traditions and research perspectives. In addition, calls for papers were announced in Turkish, English, and Arabic, enabling broad international participation. Following these multilingual calls, the submitted papers underwent a peer-review process conducted in accordance with scientific and ethical standards. As a result of the evaluations, a total of 148 papers were included in the scientific program, comprising 34 papers from Türkiye and 114 papers from 13 different countries, namely the United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Indonesia, Morocco, Palestine, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Kuwait, Egypt, Syria, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.

The studies presented in this proceedings book brought together contemporary theoretical approaches, original analyses, and diverse academic experiences from different geographical regions in the fields of language, literature, and culture. In particular, the congress clearly demonstrated the importance of international and intercultural collaborative research, emphasizing its crucial role in the universal dissemination of scientific knowledge and the establishment of sustainable interaction among different academic traditions.

In this context, researchers are encouraged to further engage in interdisciplinary studies, to strengthen academic interaction through joint projects and international co-authored publications, and to enhance the visibility of their research by producing scholarly work in multiple languages. Universities, research centers, and other stakeholders are likewise encouraged to continue supporting early-career researchers, fostering international academic networks, and developing sustainable structures for high-quality scientific production.

It is our sincere hope that this congress and the present proceedings book will contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, inspire new academic collaborations, and promote rigorous scientific research in the fields of language, literature, and cultural studies. We would like to express our gratitude to all institutions, reviewers, invited speakers, and distinguished researchers who contributed to the successful realization of this congress.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

انعقد المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغة والأدب والدراسات الثقافية في مدينة أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، وشكّل منصة علمية متميزة جمعت دراسات اللغة والأدب والثقافة في إطارٍ متعدد التخصصات. وقد نُظّم المؤتمر من قِبَل مجتمع سايبيلدر (Saybilder)، بدعمٍ علمي من عدد من مؤسسات التعليم العالي، وفي مقدمتها جامعة ماردين أرتقلو وجامعة قرطاج (Carthage University).

وشهد المؤتمر مشاركة متحدثين مدعويين من ست دول مختلفة، حيث التقى هؤلاء بنخبة من الباحثين الذين يمثلون مدارس أكاديمية ورؤى بحثية متنوعة. كما أُطلقت دعوات المشاركة باللغات التركية والإنجليزية والعربية، ما أسهم في تحقيق مشاركة دولية واسعة. وبعد ذلك، خضعت البحوث المقدّمة لعملية تحكيم علمي وفق المعايير الأكاديمية والأخلاقية المعتمدة. وأسفرت هذه العملية عن إدراج 148 بحثاً ضمن البرنامج العلمي، منها 34 بحثاً من تركيا و 114 بحثاً من 13 دولة هي: الإمارات العربية المتحدة، الجزائر، إندونيسيا، المغرب، فلسطين، العراق، إيران، قطر، الكويت، مصر، سوريا، المملكة العربية السعودية، والأردن.

وقد جمعت الدراسات الواردة في هذا الكتاب بين أحدث المقاربات النظرية، والتحليلات الأصيلة، والتجارب الأكاديمية المتنوعة من مختلف المناطق الجغرافية في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة. كما أبرز المؤتمر بوضوح أهمية البحوث القائمة على التعاون الدولي والتفاعل الثقافي، لما لها من دور محوري في تعميم المعرفة العلمية وبناء تفاعل أكاديمي مستدام بين التقاليد العلمية المختلفة.

وانطلاقاً من نتائج هذا اللقاء العلمي، يُشجّع الباحثون على توسيع نطاق الدراسات البيئية، وتعزيز المشاريع المشتركة، والإسهام في النشر العلمي الدولي المشترك، إضافة إلى الإنتاج البحثي متعدد اللغات بما يزيد من انتشار الأبحاث وتأثيرها. كما تُدعى الجامعات ومراكز البحث وسائر الشركاء الأكاديميين إلى مواصلة دعم الباحثين الشباب، وتعزيز الشبكات العلمية الدولية، وبناء هياكل مستدامة تضمن جودة واستمرارية الإنتاج العلمي.

وإذ نأمل أن يكون هذا المؤتمر وهذا الكتاب قد أسهما في إثراء الأدبيات العلمية وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، فإننا نتقدم بخالص الشكر والتقدير إلى جميع المؤسسات المشاركة، والمحكمين، والمتحدثين المدعويين، والباحثين الكرام الذين أسهموا في إنجاح هذا الحدث العلمي.

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La profanation du sacré entre capitalisme culturel et redéfinition du sacré dans un cadre postcolonial, étude de cas : « The Holly Virgin Mary » de Christ OFILI 826

Fatima Erramy

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Minhaj al-Fiqh at-Tarjamī: Riddah against Western Control of The Qur'ānic Studies

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Abstract

The absence of a clear well-defined Islamic methodology governing tarjama (translation of) the meanings of al-Qur'ān al-Karīm (TMQK) makes it difficult to assign any of the available non-Islamic approaches as reliable. This paper introduces its methodology Minhaj al-Fiqh at-Tarjamī of the meanings of Al-QK (TMQK), claiming that there is riddah against (refrain from) the biased non-Islamic, especially Western approaches that control the Qur'ānic studies discipline. Such approaches fail to be applied to al-Qur'ān al-Karīm (Al-QK), which is not a book of science, despite its scientific miracles, nor is it a book of Philosophy despite its great Hikma (wisdom), nor a book of history despite the many historical facts it contains, nor a book of poetry or literature despite its miraculous linguistic unique bayan (eloquence). Al-Minhaj is a call on the Muslim 'ulamā' (scholars) and Islamic authorities to produce a contemporary Ijmā' (consensus) that guarantees a reliable Islamic tanḏhīr (theorisation) under a global center, where TMQK is considered one of the Islamic 'ulūm (Islamic fields of knowledge). Criteria of al-Minhaj and a of reliable turjumān (translator) of TMQK are derived from the rules and criteria that An-Nabi ρ had set for TMQK during his call to non-'Arab rulers and their people to Islam. Those rules were later adopted and developed by aṣ-Ṣaḥaba (the Companions), at-Tabi'īn (the Successors), and the first Muslim 'ulamā', where Maṣadir al-Islam were the moderators.

Keywords: Minhaj, al-Fiqh at-Tarjamī, translation, al-Qur'ān, theorization

منهاج الفقه الترجمي: ردّة على سيطرة الغرب على الدراسات القرآنية

دعاء محمد أنور ديب

دكتوراه في اللغة الإنجليزية والترجمة

دار بيان للنشر والترجمة - مصر

ملخص

إنّ غياب منهجية إسلامية واضحة ومحددة تحكم ترجمة معاني القرآن الكريم يجعل من الصعب الوثوق بأيّ من المناهج غير الإسلامية المتاحة. تُقدّم هذه الورقة البحثية منهجها "منهاج الفقه الترجمي لمعاني القرآن الكريم، مؤكدةً وقوع ردّة على المناهج غير الإسلامية المتحيزة، ولا سيما الغربية منها، التي تُسيطر على مجال الدراسات القرآنية. فهذه المناهج لا يمكن تطبيقها على القرآن الكريم؛ فهو ليس كتابًا علميًا رغم ما يحويه من معجزات علمية، ولا كتابًا فلسفيًا رغم حكمته البالغة، ولا كتابًا تاريخيًا رغم ما يحتويه من حقائق تاريخية، ولا كتابًا شعريًا أو أدبيًا رغم بلاغته اللغوية الفريدة. والمنهاج هو دعوة لعلماء المسلمين إلى التوصل إلى إجماع معاصر يضمن تأطيرًا إسلاميًا موثوقًا به تحت رعاية مركز عالمي، واعتبار تراجم القرآن الكريم أحد العلوم الإسلامية. تُستمد معايير المنهاج ومعايير المترجم الموثوق به من القواعد والمعايير التي وضعها النبي ﷺ عند دعوته حكام غير العرب وشعوبهم إلى الإسلام. وقد تبني الصحابة والتابعون والعلماء الأوائل هذه القواعد وطورها، وكان مصادر الإسلام أهم المرجعيات في هذا الشأن.

الكلمات المفتاحية: المنهج، الفقه الترجمي، الترجمة، القرآن، التنظير

Introduction

Western Qur'ānic Studies, Naked Discourse of Power

There is a global movement among translation scholars facing the traditional Eurocentric vision that has dominated cultural studies. In the Qur'ānic studies, for example, De Blois (2010) confirms that the modern revisionist criticism of Al-QK is not a phenomenon of Islamic society but of "Western academic scholarship," that emerged "not from within Islam itself but from what in the East is still regarded (rightly or wrongly) as the "Christian" Occident and is perceived by modern Muslim apologists as the continuation of a long-standing Christian and Jewish enmity towards Islam, a continuation of the Crusades and of European imperialism" (p. 616).

Susan Bassnett (2002) refers to André Lefevere's statement that the goal of translation studies is to "produce a comprehensive theory which can also be used as a guideline for the production of translations," and it is vital to link theory with practice (p. 136-7). Munday (2016), on the other hand, refers to Holmes's remark on the limitations imposed at the time because translation research, lacking a home of its own, as it "was dispersed across older disciplines (languages, linguistics, etc.)" (p.10).

In fact, non-Islamic, especially Western, approaches are proven to be a failure when applied to the Qur'ānic studies. S. Parvez Manzoor (1987) regards the Qur'ānic studies of Wansbrough and Western revisionists as "a naked discourse of power" and "an outburst of psychopathic vandalism" in "a project born of spite, bred in frustration and nourished by vengeance" (pp. 33-49). Manzoor (1987) explains the reason behind that discourse is that the "greatest hour of his worldly-triumph, the Western man, coordinating the powers of the State, Church and Academia, launched his most determined assault on the citadel of Muslim faith" (pp. 33-49). For example, *The Qur'ān of The Historians (Le Coran des Historiens)*

and the scientific honesty of its entire work team are criticized by Zeinab 'Abdel 'Aziz (2021) as being "the biggest and most coward slap directed by France on Al-Qur'ān, Islam and Muslims.

Delivering the true message of Islam has always required its correct reliable tarjama through giving its right tafsīr to 'Arabic speaking Muslims, then through the correct tarjama of this tafsīr to non-'Arabic speakers. The spread of misinterpretation and unreliable translations has always led to noticeable problems. In this regard, translation of MQK into Latin in the 11th and 12th centuries, was the starting point, for an intellectual hatred, the most dangerous and effective than military wars on Islam, that has continued until the present era, based on a long account of the history of Christianity in Europe, and the history of Muslims in al-Andalus, Sicily, southern Italy, etc., as well as the history of 'Abd al-Rahman al-Ghafiqi's campaign in which he occupied half of the area of France, then the history of the Crusades (Ma'ayerjī, 2023). It is an attack of two parts; one is directed at the Christian peoples to immunize them against Islam by distorting its image, slandering it, criticizing it, insulting it, Al-Qur'ān, and an-Nabi (prophet) (Ma'ayerjī, 2023). The second part is directed at Muslims through the missionary attacks on the nation of Islam as a whole and on the Islamic countries with a specific population density, such as Nigeria, Bangladesh and Indonesia (Ma'ayerjī, 2023).

At-Tanḍhīr al-Islamī versus Worldview Theory

The paper claims that there has been a recent strong riddah against (refrain from) the Western secular non-Islamic invasion that has dominated Islamic studies for centuries. This riddah has been crystalized after what is called the Arab Spring with its free internet-based revolution. The virtual world has given a parallel chance for all trends to express their intellectual orientations.

In the past century, tension among theoretical currents started; one calling for a return to and revival of Islamic principles, and another carrying the banner of secularism and liberated humanity. In addition, as the quality assessment of tarjama is a hot topic, there are demands raised by many Western and non-Western academics for the "dewesternization" of studies of tarjama in general.

In his book, *What the Qur'an Meant: And Why It Matters*, Garry Wills, as a non-Muslim with an open mind, reads Al-QK with sympathy but with rigor, trying to discover why other non-Muslims, such as Pope Francis, find it an inspiring book, worthy to guide people down through the centuries. He opens a conversation on one of the world's most practiced religions. Wills (2017) writes,

We [ordinary Americans] blundered into the longest war in our history without knowing basic facts about the Islamic civilization with which we were dealing. We are constantly fed false information about Islam-claims that it is essentially a religion of violence, that its sacred book is a handbook for terrorists. There is no way to assess these claims unless we have at least some knowledge of the Qur'an. (Para. 2)

In fact, Western system of knowledge with its epistemological approach and methodology have dominated the Qur'ānic studies, and affected the social and cultural aspects of the Muslim world that earlier had had its own Islamic system of knowledge for centuries. In accordance to this worldview, Orientalists even developed their methodology of tafsīr of Al-QK to the extent that many Muslims have followed it.

Worldview is "a vague concept" that attempts "to explain the whole range of human experience by reference to what is most ultimately real" (Holmes, 1983, p. 52). While it cannot be scientifically proved, it is affected by culture, religion, philosophy, politics, etc. One of the worldview religious components "centers around texts, holy sacred writings, accounts or stories that educate one's worldview" (Valk, et all, 2017. p. 123). Dualism, a split-version worldview, "separates reality into two fundamentally distinct categories: holy and profane, sacred and secular" (Walsh, 1984). The modern philosophy approach comprehends the human being through "the paradigm of an immanentist, naturalistic and materialistic

theory” that reduces spiritual, emotional and cultural life to scientific formulas, which “ends by denying that any reliable claims can be made about these phenomena at all” (Mesard, 2013, p.184).

Elmessiry (1427 AH) argues that there is “a pervasive feeling amongst Arab intellectuals that the methodologies used currently in the Arab social sciences are not entirely neutral;” as being controlled by alien (foreign) Western biases (al-taḥayyuz) that shape paradigms and methods or approaches to acquiring and organising knowledge (p. xii). They are imposed through ghazw thaqafī (cultural invasion), ghazw fikrī (intellectual invasion), and al-ghazw ar-rūhī (spiritual invasion) to the norms of the Muslim society under the coercive conditions of alimbīriyaliyya al-thaqāfiyya (Western cultural imperialism), colonial and neo-colonial domination before and after the era of globalization (Elmessiry, 1427 AH. p. xii).

In addition, Elmessiry (1427 AH) believes relativism is a dangerous trend in the paradigm of Western modernity, as Nietzsche’s announcement of “the death of God” as announcing the death of man and the end of metaphysics; so, he calls for a metaphysical and moral vision organised by transcendent point of reference, and actualized through an epistemology of “Islamic relativism” (p. 13). Elmessiry calls for the creation of genuine alternative project of the Islamization of Knowledge informed by the insights of what he calls “Islamic humanism” (*al-insāniyya al-islāmiyya*) whose conceptual categories and institutional forms can be applied into societies with traditions (Mesard, 2013, p. 1). For him, Humanism must be Islamic, for Islam provides the kind of theological paradigm or imagination that can orient thought in this way.

Asad Rustam, the nominated Christian historian (d. 1965), found an objective similarity between the rules of ‘Ilm Muṣṭalaḥ al-Ḥadīth مصطلح الحديث in Islamic civilization and the rules of historical criticism in the modern European methodology. Rustam believes that the Western methodology, which appears today for the first time in a guise, is not alien to ‘Ilm al-Ḥadīth, but rather has a strong connection to it. History is knowledge first, then narration, just as Ḥadīth is knowledge and narration, and some of the rules laid down by ‘ulamā’ many centuries ago to reach the truth in Ḥadīth (‘Ilm al-Jarḥ and Ta’dīl الجرح والتعديل) or criticism and praise are consistent with the essence of some systems that European scholars later approved in building the science of methodology.

Field Studies

The researcher made some interviews with non-‘Arab Muslims, especially Turks, and asked them about their relation to AL-QK. The course of this study started with the beginning of Covid pandemic, during which the interest turned to the virtual world that provided a wide access to limitless e-libraries. The study benefited from e-research and physical activities that included attending hundreds-hour audio-visual online lectures, as well as participating in close conversations with too many Muslim ‘Ulamā’; such as:

KIM Waqf Foundation Turkiye

Actually, it is a unique experience for the researcher to be a volunteer at the KIM Waqf for introducing Islam to non-Muslim visitors of the Turkish famous mosques, especially the Suleymanie Mosque in Istanbul. The researcher interviewed and talked about Islam to tens of European, Asian and African visitors. She witnessed their great interest to know about Islam, especially after the war on Gaza took place in October 2023. They were keen to take copies of translated meanings of AL-QK.

Aş-Şaḥaba Academy

Aş-Şaḥaba Academy has built a global network of specialized professionals of Imams, sheikhs, ‘ulamā’ who serve in correcting the misleading concepts about Islam, providing a unique opportunity of hundreds of interactive Zoom and other video lectures, with different languages, mainly al-‘Arabiyya and English, in addition on Spanish, Urdu, Turkish, and other languages. Attending such lectures has widened the scopes

of this study; due to the close contact with unique many experiences of people who reverted to Islam, some of whom had been atheists, and became Callers to Islam.

Guided by Al-Qur'ān Program

Guided by Al-Qur'ān Program بالقرآن اهتديت, a TV and YouTube program, presented by Sheikh Fahd al-Kandarī, broadcasted during Ramaḍān years ago, was one of the motivators of this study. The idea of the program is about how one Aya (verse), or Ayāt of Al-QK transformed the lives of too many non-Arab natives, especially in Europe, America and Japan. One of the famous celebrities interviewed was Lauren Booth, the sister of Tony Blaire's wife. This study raises some questions; such as: how was tarjama of those Ayāt had such effect on those people's minds and hearts? What if they had known al-Arabiyya? Why we al-Arab neglect such great gift of al-Arabiyya, the language of the most sacred book on earth? What makes such huge number of Western educated upper middle-class women take their decision to revert to Islam, inspite of the effects of feminism and Islamophobia?

American Imams Academy (AIA)

It is a non-profit organization in America specialized in teaching 'Arabic and Islamic 'ulūm for both Muslims and non-Muslims. It provides unique opportunity to listen to hundreds hours of lectures and to interact with professors 'ulamā' from al-Azhar University, both in 'Arabiyya and English, teaching hot topics about al-'ulūm al-Islamiyya and their history, with focus on the currently debatable issues of the Muslims living in the West; tarjamāt Al-QK, modern tafasīr, Islamophobia, Sharī'a, etc. The unique thing is the authenticity of ṣaḥīḥ as-Sunnah as a reference when handling the most modern debatable issues.

Clubhouse

Clubhouse is a good platform for a direct contact with different groups with different stances towards Islam. It offers a unique chance for researchers to make numerous studies on multiple topics; political, social, religious, etc. Islam is the hottest of these topics. With close and active participation on Clubhouse, this study has been enriched with unique and great portion of 'ulūm through hundred hours of lectures either by professional sheikhs, 'ulamā' and scholars, or with the debates between them and other groups; such as:

Al-Ibrahīmiyya, A Religion Rejected by Sheikh Al-Azhar

Imam Al-Azhar Sheikh Aḥmad Aṭ-Ṭayyib announced his rejection of the call to the "new Abrahamic religion" saying that coexistence between adherents of different religions does not "blend Christianity, Judaism and Islam into one religion upon which people gather and rid them of the burdens of conflicts". Aṭ-Ṭayyib said that the call to "Ibrahimism" "appears to be a call for human unity and the elimination of the causes of disputes and conflicts, and in fact it is a call to confiscate freedom of belief, freedom of faith and choice" (Aṭ-Ṭayyib, 2021).

Al-Aḥmadiyya

In *Barahin-e-Ahmadiyya*, its leader Mirza Ghulam Aḥmad Al-Qadiyanī claimed: to be a prophet and Messiah, more than ten thousand verses were revealed to him, whoever denies him is an infidel, Muslims are required to perform Ḥajj to Qadiyan as the holy town like Makkah and Madīnah, etc. Mirza G. Ahmad supported the coloniser by addressing letters to the English government in India, sustaining its support by declaring his anti-jihad discourse that has made the group favourable to both the colonial Europe and the Israeli occupiers of Palestine. The British occupiers have preserved the favour of al-Aḥmadiyya and are still spreading their deviant ideas by supporting of what they call al-Aḥmadiyyah's translations of al-Qur'ān everywhere under the disguise of the so called "reformests." In 2012, Jamaat Kababir, held their formal,

annual gathering of al-Aḥmadiyya in Haifa under the umbrella of “spiritual atmosphere,” being proud of the praise they received from the former Israeli Minister Daniel Hershkowitz.

The Qur’ānists/ An-Nukraniyyūn, Sunnah Deniers, Odd Interpretations of Al-QK

Ar-Rasūl (the Messenger) ﷺ was the chief legislator, and he did not say or do except what was from Allah I kept in what is known as Sunnah, the second Waḥī (Revelation). The history of those called Qur’ānists, and who deny as-Sunnah, is known with the Orientalists, and among the likes of them were those at the days of An-Nabi ρ. Among those who deviated from Ayāt Allah Ψ. Extremist secularists spread calls for changing Aḥkam (rulings of) ash-Sharī’a under the false claims of its inappropriateness for the interests of Muslims. These calls agenda is not separate from giving wrong interpretations Ayāt Al-QK. Denying As-Sunnah is one of the aspects of the war against Islam by raising suspicions in the hearts and minds of Muslims towards tafsīr Al-QK by rejecting all Turath (the inherited Sunnah and ‘ulūm). Groups have been trained to lead such ideological wars, disguised under the name of Al-QK. They neglect the fact that those who transmitted Al-QK to us were the same Ṣaḥāba and ‘ulamā’ who transmitted As-Sunnah.

At-Takfiriyyūn and Al-Madakhela

This group do not hesitate to charge any Muslim or ‘ulamā’ of being kuffar (from blasphemy), depending on their own interpretation of the texts, either from Al-QK or Sunnah. Fahmy Howeidī expresses this in relation to the argument of the deviation of the course of Islamic history, and the confinement of the true application of Sharī’a to the stage of the Rightly Guided Caliphs, which is adhered to and promoted by extremist secularists. He says it is the same argument adopted by the advocates of Takfīr and Hijra group, who say that after Ar-Rashidūn’s stage there was a departure from Islam and a denial of Ash-Sharī’a law, which should be considered explicit kufr (Howeidī, 1420 AH. p. 46).

Atheists

During his rule, the American President Joe Biden’s administration granted Millions of dollars ‘to promote atheism worldwide’ (Keene, 2022). The funded groups active on Clubhouse are good representation of such war whose main task is to show that they have a strong existence in the Muslim world.

Energy Groups and Odd Interpretation of MQK

They mix Islamic tafsīr with their own concepts derived from Buddhist and Hindu traditions. They have been funded to spread their programs with thoughts about the falsified relation between what they call energy sciences and Islam.

Feminists and Redbills

Feminists have earlier role attacking the Bible, and even they published what they called the *The Women’s Bible*. The more problematic is the telbīs (misconception) of what is recently known as Islamic Feminism. Many debates have gone viral due to the spread of this concept. They are actually contradicting when applying the latest Feminist’ movement slogans that contradict to Islam; such as; the right of homosexuals, abortion, sexual trans gendering, equality in mirath (inheritance), attacking polygamy and calling for women’s right of polygamy.

Suspicious Applications and Hard Copies of Al-QK

Due to the easy accessibility of internet, many applications have found easy access worldwide, including those spreading misleading Ayat of Al-QK, either fully or in parts. Many warnings also spread against such applications. For example, there is a warning spread over an application named Al Quran Sharif which was downloaded for more than 500 thousand times by users over the globe. This application was developed by ZipoApps company which found to be located in the occupied territory (Tel Aviv). Al-Minhaj

downloaded the application in order to check it. Al-Minhaj found, for example, seven mistakes in the Aya 61 of Surat al-Baqara. These mistakes include at-Tashkīl, stop marks, and letter omission, etc.

Table#1 Example of a Problematic Application of ALQK

Al-Minhaj

By 2040, Islam could be the second-largest religion in the US (Willingham, 2018). There are many statistics that assert the fact that Islam is the fastest growing Dīn, which in turn, support the hypothesis of this study that, currently and in the next decades, Al-QK is and will be the most translated book worldwide. As per studies, “[t]he holy book of Islam was probably the most frequently collected Arabic book, often acquired by collectors who could not read it” (Bevilacqua, 2014).

Bevilacqua (2014) asserts that Western peoples have for centuries studied Islam and its cultures, but by “translating its most important texts, they have sought to reap the fruits of the many literary and intellectual traditions that this religion has inspired”. Needless to say, interest in Al-QK has existed since the time of its Waḥī (Revelation). This interest has been either by the new Muslims who have been keen to memorise it and to implement its provisions, or by non-Muslims who have been either attracted and interested in knowing what that miraculous book is, or who have dealt with it with special agenda of hatred and enmity.

The main Maṣadir al-Islam, mainly Al-QK and Sunnah, face the Western secular worldview. Sheikh al-Islam Muṣṭafa Ṣabrī (1441 AH) says that tarjama (translation) of the meanings of al-Qur’ān al-Karīm is one of the serious and thorny issues of ad-Dīn (religion) and al-’Ilm (Knowledge) in Islam that should not be treated as other worldly issues that flourish, and by time, expire and become abandoned (p. 28). In this regard, this paper presents its Minhaj (an approach and methodology) stemming from Islamic-based criteria for both tarjama and turjumān of the MNQ. This approach mainly considers the unique nature of divine books in general, and Al-QK in particular with its unique language; al-’Arabiyya. Minhaj TMQK follows al-’ulamā’ al-Muslimīn who had set their own methodologies and approaches for al-’ulūm al-Islamiyya, and who set the degrees of validity and weakness for every saying attributed to An-Nabi p. Al-Minhaj is not only historical but futuristic, and not only theoretical, analytical, critical, but realistic and experimental, calling for the integration of all approaches to serve humanity and reveal the truth that benefits man in this world and the Hereafter.

Fundamental Concepts of Al-Minhaj

Qaşaş Al-Qur'ān, not mere Recount nor Literary Narrative

Al-Qaşaş (the Qur'ānic stories) in Al-QK and Sunnah has its unique definition, characteristics and purposes that cannot be expressed in the word "story" used in human-made literary works. From al-Qaşaş, Muslims know what Allah Ψ did to the Jews who ate usury, or the people of Şaliḥ when they slaughtered the she-camel, or the people of Shū'aib when they mistreated the balance, or the people of Louṭ when they practiced indecency, etc.

Storytelling is specified in two categories: narrative or recount, both of which refer to events in the past. Recount is chronological and factual (nonfiction), whose structure contains orientation, series of events and reorientation, while the text does not have any complication and resolution, with the purpose to inform and entertain the reader. Narrative is an art of storytelling that is not real (fiction), whose structure contains orientation, complication, and resolution, with the moral value, and mainly to entertain the reader (Spada, 2021). On the other hand, in Al-QK, the stories are distinguished by the fact that they are all true and real, with no lies or slander, and no room for imagination, delusion, or exaggeration; because it is from the words of the All-Wise and All-Knowing; Allah Y who says, "Indeed, these are the true qaşaş" (Āl 'Imrān: 62). Hence, the difference is crystal clear between al-qaşaş al-Qur'ānī and the story which includes the meanings of imagination, exaggeration or sometimes lies.

Al-QK and Poetry, Two Corpora of Widely Different Worldviews

In comparison to any 'Arabic genre, the inimitability of the Qur'ānic grandeur literary style and sublimity is admitted by the enemies of Islam as well as its followers. The impressions and reception of al-'Arab who were the first audience of Al-QK, and who were of good knowledge of poetry are documented; such as the famous impression of Walīd ibn al-Mūghīrah. Bauer (2010) says, "the Qur'an is said to be mubīn [...] because it hardly contains any gharīb expressions or idioms that were so typical of contemporary poetry" (p. 715).

The poetic analysis is defective; as Al-QK is not in consonance with any of al-biḥār, the known regular rhythmic patterns of 'Arabic poetry. Knauf (2010) confirms that "[t]he heated debate between Vollers, Noldeke, Kahle, Fuck, and Spitaler as to whether the consonantal text of the Qur'an reflects a local Meccan dialect or seventh-century Standard Arabic leads to a dead end" (p. 247). Al-QK, contrary to both pre-and early Islamic Arabia or modern poetry, "does not use meter, and its rhyme follows different parameters" (Bauer, 2010, p. 703-5). In addition, the two most important stylistic devices in Arabic poetry were a "specific form of metonymy (الكناية), and the simile (تشبيه), by contrast, "metaphors, parables, and allegory play a prominent role in the Qur'an, but play virtually no role in poetry" (2010, p. 703-5). Moreover, the "two corpora" of Al-QK and modern poetry reflect "a widely different worldview;" either of their pursue of different "ends" and "themes," their using language, their notable differences in content, that "hardly any similarities are to be found" (Bauer, 2010, pp. 703-705).

Al-Qur'ān Al-Karīm is not a Book of History

Although it is full of main historical events and characters, from the first creation of Adam, in addition to prophecies of the events and characters to appear in the future till Yaum Al-Qiyyamah (the Day of Judgement), Al-Minhaj asserts that Al-QK can never be treated as a book of history. Non-Islamic approaches may read Al-QK as "an epigraphic text from the early seventh century, and not through the lens of later Islamic interpretations" (Retsö, 2010. p. 284). Admitting that their knowledge of the religious history of the pre-Islamic of the 'Arabian Peninsula is "considerably poorer than it appeared to be as

recently as a generation ago;” they claim, “the relevant information originates almost entirely from Islamic sources” (Seidensticker, 2010, p. 293).

Genuinely Arabian Culture of Writing

Many studies strive to remove the attribute of al-‘Arabiyya from al-‘Arab before Islam, neglecting Islamic references and sources, and avoiding the ‘Arabic grammatical traditions and derivations. Theodor Noldeke points to the Syriac derivation of the Islamic terms, such as his treatment of the word “labbayka,” while “Wansbrough supposes the Qur’an to have come into existence at approximately the end of the second/eighth century” (Seidensticker, 2010, pp. 297 & 317).

Al-Qur’ān Al-Karīm Knowledge and Science

Al-QK exhorts us to know the sciences of the universe and the artifacts of the world to benefit from everything in existence, (Az-Zarqanī, 1995, p. 25). That is why the Muslim ‘ulamā’ have stated that learning these cosmic sciences and mastering these artistic industries are one of the obligations of competencies as long as they need them for the benefit of the individual or the group; as An-Nabi ρ said, “the strong believer is better than the weak believer, and in both of them there is good” (Az-Zarqanī, 1995, p. 25). It is true that Al-QK contains many scientific facts, but it is not a book of science nor of philosophy, although Islam has a vision to give better answers to the basic questions in philosophy.

Definitely, Al-QK has created unique ‘ulūm with unique scopes, definitions and criteria. ‘Ulūm Al-QK are independent ‘ulūm that deal with research related to Al-QK in terms of knowing the reasons for Al-Waḥī (the revelation), its collection and arrangement, knowledge of al-Makkī and al-Madanī, an-Nasikh (the abrogating) and al-Mansūkh (the abrogated), al-Muḥkam and al-Mutashabih, and all other things related to it. This ‘ilm (‘Ulūm) may be called ‘Uṣūl at-Tafsīr; because it deals with topics that al-Mufassir must know (As-Sadah, 2023. p. 20).

Al-QK has always been the engine driving Muslim intellectuals and ‘ulamā’, providing endless benefits gained through Tafsīr, and creating unique ‘ulūm and manahij (plural of Minhaj). In fact, Al-‘ulūm al-Islamiyya in general and ‘ulūm Al-QK in particular have a great attention in Sunnah that had already placed their foundations that flourished through the Muslim civilization that has greatly affected all other civilizations with which Islam interacted. Abū Ad-Dardā’ τ said, “Rasūl Allah ρ left us, and there was no bird flying with its wings in the sky but that he mentioned to us knowledge about it” (At-Tuwajirī, 1414 AH. p. 18). When Al-QK calls Muslims to learn valuable knowledge and master the worldly sciences (astronomy, cosmology, etc.), this actually reflects its strength, although none of these worldly sciences is a comprehensive ‘ilm, and although it was not revealed to prove any of the theories of these sciences, nor to establish one of their laws (Az-Zarqanī, 1995, p. 27).

Findings and Recommendations:

Tarjamet MQK, a Project of al-Ummah

Al-Minhaj criticizes the individual attempts to translate MQK; as no humanbeing can ever undertake alone the task of conveying the true meanings of Al-QK. Al-Mufassirūn al-Muslimūn themselves who speak the language of Al-QK differ in tafsīr of many words. To attribute tarjamet MQK to one or more persons, this study claims, is one of the critical problems. Al-Minhaj sets the first condition of a reliable Tarjama of the MNQ that it is not named after one Turjuman, but to be under the supervision of an authorized Ijmā’, to avoid problems that may be due to the personality of at-turjumān, the intellectual orientation, ideology, etc. Al-Minhaj calls for establishing a body that defines the criteria of Turjumān of MQK, just as the case of the famous ‘ilm al-Jarḥ wa Ta’dīl.

Al-Minhaj calls for examining all manoeuvres and disciplined approaches to Al-QK by the first Mufasssīrīn regarding the Qur'ānic terminology that they were not in accord on. Al-Minhaj does not start from the scratch; as al-'ulamā' al-Muslimūn had set conditions for al-'ulūm al-Islamiyya, Ijtihad in TMQK has been present in the models, tools and conditions they set. Al-Minhaj recommends:

- establishing The Interactive Portal of al-'Ulūm al-Islamiyya, specified for researchers and students of al-'Ulūm al-Islamiyya and 'ulūm Al-QK including its tarjamat.
- creating special logarithms or a specific method to show at-Tashkīl and stop-signs to create a sort of map keys for them; so that the reader becomes accustomed to them.
- the co-operation of all trusted available Islamic entities to reach the desired co-operation that serves Islam and delivering its true message.

Global Center and Portal for Serving Al-'Ulūm Al-Islamiyya

As there is an Islamic committee for reviewing the editions of the Muṣḥaf (written Qur'ān), there is a need for a global committee designated to review TMNQ into any language. In the age of big mess of sources due to the spread of and the easy accessibility to the internet, the challenge of reaching reliable sources is very high. However, a reliable tarjama of MQK is possible under the umbrella of a balanced 'Ijmā' (consensus) if there are two main factors available: a central theoretical approach of at-Tarjamāt al-Islamiyya, and a global central body or organization for the history and studies of al-'Ulūm al-Islamiyya and Tarjama. The Center is an international body for all Islamic studies: Qur'ānic, Sunnah, Sīrah, culture, jurisprudential, biography, I'jāz, sciences, etc. It shall include its members of specialists in al-'Ulūm Al-Islamiyya of Naql (Transmitted Knowledge) and 'Aql (Reason) who are able to establish the criteria of tarjamet MQK.

There have been many calls for a strong stance by Muslim 'Ulamā' that includes fundraising, raising competition by establishing prizes that increase the value of at-Turjuman, developing methodologies, etc. Al-Ma'ayrjī's highlights the role of the Latin translations and their sequels that erected a barrier between the Europeans and the pure meanings of Al-QK, which lead to inherited intense enmity and hatred of Islam and Muslims. He calls on the Islamic Ummah to adopt the idea of "The International Organization for the Holy Quran" or "the International Qur'ān Foundation" emanating from the Muslim World Conference supported by the Islamic world financially, and giving it a moral character, enabling it to speak in the name of Al-QK on behalf of all Muslims. It represents the Islamic world in the service of Al-QK, its publication and distribution, printing, tafsīr, tarjama, defending it, revealing distortion, and monitoring and combating corrupt translations issued in the world. This center will be a reliable reference for a reliable tarjama of the MQK, as-Sunnah and as-Sīrah.

Rules of Minhaj al-Fiqh at-Tarjamī of the Meanings of Al-Qur'ān Al-Karīm

Al-QK was transmitted to this day without adding a letter or subtracting a letter. Al-Minhaj coins between TMQK and Al-Fiqh in Islam during setting the rules for a reliable Tandhīr of TMQK, under the title الفقه الترجي لمعاني القرآن الكريم (Al-Fiqh At-Tarjamī of MQK). Al-Minhaj sets main criteria for TMQK:

Maṣadir Al-Islam Prior to Foreign References

In Islamic jurisprudence, Sharī'a is considered to make rules for every aspect of life; economic, social, religious, etc. It is agreed upon among the majority of al-Fuqahā' (Muslim jurists) that primary Maṣadir Al-Islam (the sources of Islamic legislation) are four: Al-QK, as-Sunnah an-Nabawiyyah (Sunnah), al-'Ijmā' (Consensus), al-Qiyās (Analogical Reasoning), then come al-Istiḥsān, al-Maṣlaḥah al-Mursalāh (Public Interest), al-'Urf (Custom), Shar' of our predecessors, maḥab of aṣ-Ṣaḥabī. المصلحة، والاستصحاب، والمصلحة. (Ouda, 2013, p. 164). وشرع من قبلنا، ومذهب الصحابي

Islamic Definitions are Based only on Maşadir Al-Islam

Definition is one of the problematic issues in every discipline in which difference in languages, cultures and ideologies plays an important role; especially in the discipline of translation of religious texts in general, and of tarjamāt maʿānī Al-QK in particular. Al-Minhaj depends on the Islamic definition of tanḍhīr (theorization), not on the Platonic Philosophic definition that separates between theory and ʿilm. At-Tanḍhīr for a reliable Tarjama of the meanings of Al-QK is rigorously Islamic and that has existed in the Islamic history. It cannot be named after any Western or Eastern names; not Chomskian, nor Derridian, or Bakhtinian, etc.

As-Sunnah an-Nabawiyya, al-Waḥī ath-Thānī

Islam is not limited to Al-QK, but it includes as-Sunnah an-Nabawiyyah/ al-Ḥadīth, the second of Maşadir al-Islam that springs from Al-QK. As-Sunnah is the first Tafsīr that safeguards the meanings of Al-QK, and both constitute the law of every issue in Muslim life. As well as there have been al-ʿulūm al-Islamiyya that sprung from Al-QK, there have been al-ʿulūm that have been developed to protect, to serve and provide Tafsīr of as-Sunnah; such ʿulūm Al-Ḥadīth.

Al-Ḥadīth Al-Qudsī and An-Nabawī, Not “Tradition”

Some ʿulamāʾ call al-Aḥadīth al-Qudsiyya as Illahiyya or Rabāniyya as related to Allah Y. The word is derived from the verb Qaddassa (sanctification). In terminology, it is what An-Nabi ρ narrates As-Sanad (on the authority) of Allah Y. It has special provisions that differ from the provisions of Al-QK. While Allah Y challenged al-ʿArab with Al-QK, and this challenge will continue until Yaum Al-Qiyamah (the Day of Judgment), Al-Ḥadīth Al-Qudsī was not challenged by nor miraculous.

Al-Ijmāʾ, Al-Qiyās and Al-Ijtihād

An-Nabi ρ said, “My people will never agree on an error”. This Ḥadīth is the base for al-Ijmāʾ (scholarly consensus). As one of Maşadir Al-Islam, al-Ijmāʾ means “the agreement of the mujtahidīn of the Muslim ʿUmah after the death of An-Nabi ρ, in a certain time, on ḥukm sharʿī (an Islamic legal ruling), and it refers to the existence of reliable legal evidences. Al-Ijmāʾ is within al-ʿUmah Al-Islamiyya because it is on the issues of ḥalal (the permissible) and ḥaram (the forbidden) from al-Aḥkam ash-Sharʿiyyah (the legal rulings) (Al Saif, 1435 AH)¹. The opinions of non-Muslims are not taken into consideration, even if they are familiar with al-ʿUlūm al-Islamiyya; because the issue is legislation in ad-Dīn (Mussallam, 1435 AH).

Al-Qiyās (Analogical Reasoning) is one of the rational types of evidence of Islamic Tashrīʿa (jurisprudence), and it is one of Maşadir al-Aḥkam (the sources of rulings) agreed upon in Islam. Al-Qiyās is “the effort of the mujtahid to extract the truth,” (Aş-Şaliḥ, 2020) and applying a case whose ḥukm (rule) is not found by a text to a case whose rule is found in the text on account of equation of both cases in respect of effective cause of al-ḥukm, on the basis of the equality between effective causes found in the two cases (Islamic Bankers).

An-Nabi ρ trained aş-Şaḥāba and the Muslims in his time on legal thinking methods similar to analogy. For example, “A woman came to Rasūl Allah ρ requesting him to give her fatwa (a legal opinion). She said, “Ay Rasūl Allah! my father died and performance of Ḥajj was due to him. May I perform al-Ḥajj on his behalf?” Rasūl Allah ρ said, “Tell me! If your father owed a debt and you paid it, would that benefit him?” She replied, “yes”. Rasūl Allah ρ said, “Perform al-Ḥajj on his behalf, the debt due to Allah deserves most to be paid” (Islamic Bankers).

Aş-Şaḥāba, at-Tabīʿīn and al-ʿUlamāʾ al-Muslimūn founded the basic strong methods for two main Maşadir of Islam; Al-QK and Sunnah from the early years of Islam. Al-ʿIjmaʾ is of Maşadir Al-Islam, and if there are

different opinions among al-'ulama' al-Muslimin about a specific matter, it is a positive diversity of opinions that gives new possibilities and flexibilities about this matter. However, it must be clear that they all are following al-'Ijma' about the bases of this matter in Islam. Imam Ash-Shāfi'i and other 'ulamā' developed a set of principles to systematise legal thinking of Uṣūl al-Fiqh for Tafsīr the meanings of Al-QK and al-Ḥadīth, based on the texts of these two main Maṣadir employing the tools such as al-Qiyās.

Al-Ijtihad is one of the main Islamic principles and practices since the time of An-Nabi ρ that have been developed by al-'Ulamā' as an application of the flexible nature of Islam that endorses reasoning based upon Maṣadir al-Islam in order to maintain a balanced life for Muslims. Ijtihād, in Islamic law, is the independent or original interpretation of problems not precisely covered by Al-QK, al-Ḥadīth, and Ijmā'. Ijtihad literally means "to strive, put one-self out, work hard". In Islamic legal terminology it means "the process of deriving the laws of the Sharī'ah from its sources" (Rizvi). There is a false claim raised by the Orientalists, "In Qur'anic studies, it seemed, the gate of ijtihād had been closed and the discipline could from now on devote itself to administrating the accumulated knowledge of earlier pioneers," as if "Qur'anic studies had become a subject that was bound to bore itself to death" (Sinai, et al., 2010, p. 2). This claim is refuted by presenting many examples that prove that ijtidah is an ongoing main principle in Islamic studies in general.

As-Sīrah an-Nabawiyya

As-Sīrah is the study of the life of An-Nabi ρ; his Aḥadīth, news, actions, morals, qualities, and reports, from his birth until his death, as well as the life and news of his Ṣaḥāba τ in general. It is concerned with the evidence of his Nubuwah (Prophecy), and the conditions of his time, and his approval of the actions of his Ṣaḥāba τ (As-Salami, p. 4). As-Sīrah is a valuable source of information for the early period of Islam and understanding Qur'anic material. As-Sīrah and al-Ḥadīth contain isnad (chains of transmission). While al-Ḥadīth is not concerned with an event, and normally does not specify a time or place;" as its purpose lies in its being "an authoritative source of Islamic law," as-Sīrah may carry some legal or theological implications, but its main aim is to convey information about a certain event" (Wikipedia, Sīrah). As-Sīrah covers al-ghazawat (battles) of an-Nabi ρ, of aṣ-Ṣaḥāba who made Jihad (struggled) with him, and at-Tabi'in (successors) until the expansion of Muslim territory and the non-Muslims' acceptance of Islam.

Al-'Arabiyya, the Chosen Language of the Chosen Book

Across the world, the number of al-'Arabiyya (one of the six official languages) speakers exceeds the 300 million native Arabic speakers. The number of words in al-'Arabiyya without repetition- whether used or neglected- is very huge when compared to the number of words in the most prominent languages as follows (Ahmed, 2018):

Al-'Arabiyya 1,2302,912 words

English: 600,000 words

German: 160,000 words

French: 150,000 words

Russian: 130,000 words

Al-'Arabiyya is one of the richest languages in the world. One of the characteristics of the language is that it is not only constant but also evolving. Al-'Arabiyya is distinguished by its originality and permanence as one of the least languages to borrow from other languages, and to be flexible enough to absorb foreign vocabularies. This means that "the Arab today understands a poetic poem 1500 years ago because it is the

same language that Imru' al-Qays, Antara and other pre-Islamic poets spoke, and the language has preserved its letters, movements and roots" (Tcarnaev, 2017).

Al-QK and al-'Arabiyya are closely related; as the attack on its language is an attack on Allah's Book, which falsely claimed to contain non-'Arabic words. Allah Y says, "بِلِسَانٍ عَرَبِيٍّ مُبِينٍ" (In a clear 'Arabic tongue [language])" (Ash-Shū'ārā':195). By 'Ijmā' of al-'ulamā', in Al-QK, there is no speech combined of two or more non-'Arabic words, but there are "names of non-'Arabic figures" such as: Nūh, Lūṭ, Isra'īl, Jibrīl, Imrān, Isma'īl and Ibrahīm (As-Sadah, 2023, p. 67). However, al-'Ulamā' have disagreed on specifying these words. Some 'Ulamā' say Al-QK contains not only every 'Arabic dialect, but rather it contains the common languages at the time of its revelation, and this is one of its advantages as revealed to all people.

Naom Chomsky is one of the world's prominent contemporary theoreticians, whose theory of universal grammar left marks in the fields of linguistics, psychology, philosophy, and politic. He gives the hypothesis that the future may be for al-'Arabiyya or the Chinese as it was before for Latin, and later to English. Then he confesses that one of his serious errors in his own life had to do with Arabic 75 years ago when he was a student. Despite he learnt al-'Arabiyya, he learnt it to be able to read newspapers, the books, and to converse with the people. He, unfortunately, over these years, did not give it the right attention. This, according to Chomsky, has left a great gap in his understanding of the world and his ability to comprehend critical elements of the world, a mistake he says, "I shouldn't have made. I do not think that others should make" (Chomsky, 2021).

Al-Qur'ān Al-Karīm, An Addition to Al-'Arabiyya

Al-QK is said to be the supreme mainstay of al-'Arabiyya, the language of al-'Arab, which owes its survival and integrity to Al-QK, and it derives its 'ulūm from it despite their diversity and abundance. Al-QK is the first 'Arabic book committed to writing, that "signifies an important transitional stage in the history of Arabic language and literature;" as Al-QK "witnessed and actively contributed to a transformation of literary culture from a predominantly oral to a written one" (Dayeh, 2010. p. 469). Fourteen hundred years after its Wahī, Al-QK is still and will remain read and recited in 'Arabic till the Day of Judgement by millions of Muslims without any change or modifications. Al-QK has had a unique impact on the Muslims' intellectual, social, political and moral lives for centuries, with its unique language al-'Arabiyya that lived its heydays on their tongues.

Learning Al-'Arabiyya is from Ad-Dīn

Kitāb Allah was revealed in the 'Arabic tongue, and Allah's Messenger ρ conveyed the Book in the 'Arabic tongue. Therefore, al-'Arabiyya was a reason to master Ad-Dīn and knowing its tongue became part of Ad-Dīn to know about Allah Ψ and how to establish the rituals (Al-Oud. p. 1/33). There is 'Ijmā' to support what came in the decision of Hay'at Kibar al-'Ulamā' - هيئة كبار العلماء in Saudi 'Arabia that it is not permissible to change ar-Rasm al-'Othmani of al-Muṣḥaf that must remain steadfast without any taḥrīf in the Qur'ānic text, following the footsteps of aṣ-Ṣaḥāba and the Imams of the predecessors and at-Tabi'īn τ. Every Muslim is obligated to learn al-'Arabiyya to be able to read Al-QK in ar-Rasm al-'Othmani, as it was revealed in its mother tongue. Hence, Islam remains the perpetual source for Arabic (islamonline.net).

Warding off Evil Takes Precedence over Bringing Interests

The rule “درء المفسد مُقَدِّمٌ على جلب المصالح” is applied in learning and teaching Al-QK. Writing of ‘Arabic texts of Al-QK in another language has been an issue under dispute. Many ‘ulamā’ have taken strong stances against a process they see as “undoubtedly one of the greatest means of obliterating and ripping Al-Qur’ān, and in this way it is subject to change, alteration and distortion” dressed up in a shiny dress that they called: “facilitating the reading of the Qur’an for non-Arabs,” a trick that has deceived “the simple and some of the short-thinking of today’s scholars” (Al-‘Oud, p. 15). This may lead every people to have their own Qur’ān written in their letters.

Every Work about Al-Qur’ān Al-Karīm is not Qur’ān

Al-Nawawi says in *Al-Majmū’* (Ash-Sharkawī, 2013), “Tarjamet Al-Qur’ān is not Qur’ān by ‘Ijmā’ al-Muslimīn, and the attempt to prove it is inordinate; [... and] the one who speaks the meaning of al-Qur’ān in Hindi is not Qur’ān.” There is no dispute that Al-Qur’ān is miraculous, and at-tarjama is not miraculous. Wild (2010a) considers “in any translation of the Quran its most vital characteristics are lost. What is called “a translation of the Quran can never be a translation [it is merely an] English Translation of the Meanings of the Holy Quran”. The traditionalist Muslim scholars “insist that no translation is more than an exegesis (tafsir)” (Wild, 2010a).

Tafsīr Prior to Tarjama

Tafsīr Al-QK finds its source materials in many ‘ulūm; such as ‘Ilm al-lugha (language), Naḥwu (grammar), Şarf (morphology), Bayan (art or science of eloquence), Balagha (Eloquence and Rhetoric), Tashrī’āt (legal sources), al-Qira’āt, An-Naskh, etc. Al-Minhaj recommends using approaches of Tarjama that match the uniqueness of Kitab Allah Y, with special use of at-Tarjama at-Tafsīriyyah; which is seen the closest approach to serve Maqaşid (the purposes) of Al-QK.

Tafsīr, not Exegesis, nor Interpretation nor Hermeneutics

Al-Minhaj, on the other hand, is concerned with only Islamic concepts of Tafsīr instead of: explanation, interpretation, exegesis, commentary on Al-QK.

Denial of al-I’jāz al-Bayanī, a Denial of An-Nibiwwah

Denial of al-I’jāz al-Bayanī (the rhetoric miracle of al-QK) is a denial of An-Nibiwwah.

What Reader/Listener of Al-Qur’ān cannot be Ignorant of

Al-Minhaj defines criteria for the reader and the listener of Al-QK derived from Maşadir al-Islam, regarding main issues; (ما لا يسع لقارئ وسامع القرآن جهله); such as al-Aḥkam ash-Shar’iyyah that a Muslim cannot be ignorant of them. Al-‘Ulamā’, in Ijmā’ (unanimously) have agreed that it is obligatory to learn al-‘Arabiyya, and the one who fights al-‘Arabiyya is fighting the language that Allah Ψ chose for His Book. The reader of Al-QK shall not be ignorant of the general meanings of al-Ayāt, as well as ‘Ālamāt at-Tashkīl (diacritics), ‘Ālamāt al-waqf and al-waşl (stop signs), Qur’ānic orthography, inscription with al-‘Arabiyya, etc.

Criteria of A Reliable At-Turjumān Al-Faqīh of MQK

According to the criteria set for Turjumān MQK, he/she shall be aware of all the Islamic ‘ulūm related to Al-Qur’ān and As-Sunnah. They also shall be aware of the hidden agenda of the enemies of Islam theories to spread false claims disguised under multiple cloaks; such as those who call themselves Qur’ānists. Turjumān MQK must be aware of the history of the translations that were carried out by the enemies of Islam. Al-Minhaj sets and collects the criteria of Turjumān MQK who is to be equipped with special

prerequisites in order to achieve "albayan attarjami" (Translation generated truth) which upholds al-byaniyya theory of Al-QK. The wondrous "un-translatability of the Holy Quran constitutes the core and the theoretical frame of such theory," which considers "man simulated and the human being words as too shallow to allow imitation, duplication or replication processes" of Al-QK (Zahid, 2015).

At-Turjumān, Not a Translator/ Interpreter

The definitions of words "translator" and "interpreter" are always derived from the standard ancient Greek or Latin lexicographical sources; such as the Greek Hermēneus which is according to the Liddell Scott Lexicon "both these words are directly derived from the name of the god Hermes," who is seen as "an active force of nature, as fulfilling an active need of nature: to explain, to clarify, to translate, to interpret" (Gross, 2009, p. 10). In al-Minhaj, the conscience of at-Turjumān and declaring the intention are fundamental.

Al-Minhaj uses the word Turjumān instead of the words translator and interpreter which have negative image; such as in the old Greek definitions. The term at-Turjumān, which has its 'Arabic roots, has a positive history in the Western thought as well. Al-Minhaj refers to the term "dragoman" used to refer to the translator or the interpreter. Its origin refers to: "Middle English drugeman, from Anglo-French, from Old Italian dragomanno, from Middle Greek dragomanos, from Arabic tarjumān, from Aramaic tūrgēmānā," (merriam-webster) Spanish: Trujaman, French: Trucheman, Latin: Dragumannus, Aramaic: Turgemana, etc. (Gross, 2009, p. 11).

In al-'Arabiyya al-Fuṣḥā, the word Turjumān refers to the Muslim who is faqīh (specialised with knowledge) in Tarjamet MQK. The model for Turjumān MQK is derived from the story of 'Abd Allah Ibn 'Abbās τ, who was known for his knowledge of Tafsīr and was named "Turjumān Al-Qur'ān Al-Karīm". He was the cousin of An-Nabi ρ, and one of the most narrating companions of him. Upon the death of Ar-Rasūl ρ, Ibn Abbas τ was 13 or 15 years old. Ibn 'Abbās τ gave Tafsīr of Surat al-Baqarah, Ayāh by Ayāh and letter by letter. The main criteria needed in Turjumān MQK can be presented in the following points:

An-Nabi's ρ made dua' for Ibn 'Abbās:

"اللهم فقهه في الدين وعلمه التأويل".

"O Allah, grant him Fiqh in Ad-Dīn and teach him at-Ta'wīl."

Ta'wīl here means Tafsīr of Al-QK. The abundance of Ibn 'Abbās' knowledge was the reason behind his attribute "al-Baḥr" (the Sea), the greatest imam of al-Mufasserīn. Aṣ-Ṣaḥāba τ and al-'ulamā' al-Muslimūn had set criteria for Al-Mufasserīn (the practitioners of Tafsīr) considering Tafsīr to be the most important of 'ulūm al-QK. Al-Minhaj follows the same criteria of Tafsīr and try to apply them in Tarjamet MQK considering it a separate 'ilm of 'ulūm Al-QK due to its extreme importance.

The concept of Fiqh is very unique in Islam that requires full understanding of matters in ad-Dīn based on both heart and mind. It does not only require at-Turjman to just have the necessary linguistic skills ability to read al-'Arabiyya, but to be specialised in al-'ulūm al-Islamiyya in order to be able to get al-Fiqh. It should be an obligatory task on any person who bears the responsibility of tarjamet MQK to read in and learn about these 'ulūm derived from Maṣadir Al-Islam.

Al-Minhaj has tried to compile the main criteria set by 'ulamā' at-Tafsīr for al-Faqīh such as: baṣīrah (Insight), having Islamic committed background, and to have enough knowledge of the ideas and principles related to daily Islamic culture, to obtain good knowledge of secrets of the Qur'ānic expressions, to have knowledge of 'ulūm Al-QK and Ḥadīth; especially that Tufassir, knowledge of the specifications and backgrounds of each Tafsīr, (Mu'atazilī, Shī'ī, Qadiyanī, etc.) which affect the understanding of words and

their Tarjama., knowledge of Sirat (biography of) An-Nabi ρ and his Şahaba τ, which helps know Asbab an-Nizūl (the reasons of revelation) and as-Siyyaq (the context), knowledge of ‘Ilm al-Qira’āt, knowledge about ‘Ilm at-Tawḥīd (Monotheism), Ilm ‘Uşūl ad-Dīn (The Principles of Belief/ Theology), ‘Ilm Al-Fiqh Al-Akbar (jurisprudence), ‘Ilm Asmā’ and Şifat (Names and Attributes) of Allah Y, and ‘Ilm principles of ‘Usūl As-Sunnah, ‘Ilm An-Nasikh, etc. Without these ‘Ulūm, both al-Mufassir and at-Turjumān may fall into error regarding legal rulings, at-Tafsīr at-Tashrī’ī (Legal): the manner in which Ahkām are derived and proven, knowledge of at-Tarīkh (History), knowledge of the times and places of revelation of Al-Ayāt, knowledge of the condition of Jews and Christians in Jazīrat al-‘Arab (the Arabian Peninsula) during Revelation of Al-QK, knowledge of the customs and human nature of al-‘Arab to understand many Ayāt that are related to important ahkām; such as al-Jizīyah, aṭ-ṭalaq (divorce), malak al-yamīn, mirāth, ḍarb, etc., professional knowledge of the nature of al-‘Arabiyya (Mu’ajim (Lexicology), ‘Ilm ad-dalalah (Semantics), ‘Ilm an-Naḥw (علم النحو, i.e., syntax), ‘Ilm aş-Şarf and Tashkīl al-Aşwaṭ al-Kalamiyyah (morphology), ‘Ilm ‘uşūl al-Kalimat (Etymology), ‘ulūm al-Balagha (Eloquence and Rhetorics), sound, syntactic, semantic, communicative issues of the two languages.

The Application of Al-Minhaj

Muḥammad ρ is Nabi/ Rasūl, not A Prophet/ Messenger, al-Umi, *an Illiterate Man*

There have been prejudicial notions circulating since medieval and Middle Ages times about an-Nabi Muḥammad ρ overloaded with legendary and polemical stories. The theoretical approaches have not left any detail about him without alteration. One example is when the Western studies deal with the difference between the two words “rasūl” (as claimed “messenger”) and “Nabi” (as claimed “prophet”). They are used today to refer to An-Nabi Muḥammad ρ without differentiation in meaning. Khoury’s German translation of the Qur’an, “at one point even translates rasūl as “prophet” (Q 38:14)!” (Bobzin, 2010. p. 567). This is despite the sound linguistic principle that the two different expressions “are likely to carry different meanings” (Bobzin, 2010. p. 567).

The method of understanding of prophethood current in modern Western theology regards “a prophet is someone inspired or at least authorized by God and charged with the task of proclaiming a particular message concerning the future. This message can be socio-political in nature, as was the case with the classical biblical prophets” who “were not themselves politicians” (Bobzin, 2010, p. 568). Admittedly, “attempting to understand the nature of Muhammad’s prophethood on the basis of biblical precedents is a questionable method” and a decisive “mistake” (Bobzin, 2010, p. 568).

For the Western approaches, the difference between the prophet and the messenger is based on what they call the nature of true prophecy of Judeo-Christian intertexts. Such approaches try to negate the prophecy of an-Nabi Muḥammad ρ. They also consider the rule of thumb “Not every Nabi is a rasūl, but each rasūl is a Nabi” and consider it as “not strictly true” (Bobzin, 2010, p. 572). Based also on Jewish tradition, they negate prophecy from an-Nabi Muḥammad ρ claiming that prophets “do not seek political power,” while an-Nabi Muḥammad ρ practised politics. The same is done when accusing an-Nabi ρ of having “fleshly desires” when Western approaches falsely deal with his multi-marriage, with special false focus and interpretation of his “marriage to the beautiful Zaynab bint Jaḥsh.” Such approaches of fake interpretations based on Judeo-Christian intertexts affect the understanding of Ayāt, and hence, on Tarjamāt of these Ayāt. That is why Minhaj recommends the use the words as pronounced in al-‘Arabiyya; Nabi and Rasūl confirming the I’jāz (miraculousness) of Al-QK which does not use the expression “nabi Allah”. Accordingly, “it is a sound linguistic principle that two different expressions are likely to carry different meanings, so that it may be supposed that the expression “seal of the prophets” in the Seal Verse was not used without reason (Bobzin, 2010, p. 567). The “word “messenger” occurs 332 times, four times

as often as “prophet” (75 occurrences) (Bobzin, 2010, p. 567). The non-Islamic concepts, while insist that “the prophets were not themselves politicians,” attempt “to understand the nature of Muhammad’s prophethood on the basis of biblical precedents is a questionable method” (Bobzin, 2010, p. 567).

An-Nabi ρ remained illiterate until the end of his life, and illiteracy was a miracle for him. Some ‘Ulamā’ argued that An-Nabi ρ learned to read and write at the end of his life, as evidenced by the fact that he erased his name from the Treaty of Ḥudaybiyya when ‘Alī τ refused to erase it. By doing so, they wanted to remove illiteracy from him, as if it were an attribute of deficiency. The truth is that he did not need that as illiteracy is a sign of praise for him, while it is a sign of deficiency for others; because the one who taught him was not human (As-Sadah, 2023, p. 47).

There is no doubt that al-‘Arab were an illiterate nation, who were not good at reading, writing, nor arithmetic. There was only a small group who were good at writing. Historians almost agree that Quraysh in Makkah did not take over al-khaṭ (writing) except through Ḥarb bin Umayyah bin ‘Abd Shams, who was one of Asiyād (the prominent masters of) Quraysh and Kenana in Makkah, the father of aṣ-Ṣaḥabī Abū Sufyān τ, and the grandfather of aṣ-Ṣaḥabī Muawiyah τ. Ḥarb and his family were the reason for the introduction of ‘Arabic writing to Makkah. Writing remained in the hands of a few of them, until Islam appeared (As-Sadah, 2023, p. 104).

فقد أخرج البخاري τ ومسلم τ عن النبي ρ أنه قال: "إِنَّا أُمَّةٌ أُمِّيَّةٌ، لَا نَكْتُبُ وَلَا نَحْسِبُ الشَّهْرَ هَكَذَا وَهَكَذَا". يَعْني مَرَّةً تِسْعَةً وَعِشْرِينَ، وَمَرَّةً ثَلَاثِينَ".

An-Nabi ﷺ said, "We are an illiterate nation; we neither write, nor calculate the month like this and this, i.e. sometimes of 29 days and sometimes of thirty days."

This Ḥadīth means that the ummah of An-Nabi ρ in order to define the times of our fasting or our ‘Ibadah (worship) does not need a book or calculation, as is the case for other nations. There is no prohibition in this Ḥadīth on learning the book and calculation at all or other useful sciences.

In this Ḥadīth, there is no prohibition of learning the book and arithmetic or other useful sciences. Ibn Taymiyyah said, “So his [An-Nabi ρ] saying, “We are an illiterate nation” is not a request, for they were illiterate before Islam, as Allah Ψ says,

"هُوَ الَّذِي بَعَثَ فِي الْأُمِّيَّةِ رَسُولًا مِّنْهُمْ يَتْلُو عَلَيْهِمْ آيَاتِهِ وَيُزَكِّيهِمْ وَيُعَلِّمُهُمُ الْكِتَابَ وَالْحِكْمَةَ وَإِنْ كَانُوا مِن قَبْلُ لَفِي ضَلَالٍ مُّبِينٍ"

He [Allah] is the One Who emitted for the illiterate ‘people’ a messenger from among themselves—reciting to them His revelations, purifying them, and teaching them the Book and wisdom, for indeed they had previously been clearly astray. (Al-Jum’ah- 2)

Normally, in the nation to which Allah I sent His Nabi ρ, there were many who could read and write, as it was the case in most of his Ṣaḥaba who could calculate and write, such as Abū Bakr, ‘Omar, ‘Othmān, ‘Alī, Zaid, and Mu’awiyah, and other who wrote Al-Waḥī (Revelations), and wrote his letters to people, kings, and the heads of the sects, and to his workers, governors, powers, and so on. Moreover, An-Nabi ρ was sent with the statutes that contained calculations.

The following Ayāt are very significant as an answer for any exclamation about the reason for the illiteracy of An-Nabi ρ. Allah Ψ says,

وَمَا كُنْتَ تَتْلُو مِنْ قَبْلِهِ مِنْ كِتَابٍ وَلَا تَخُطُّهُ بِيَمِينِكَ إِذًا لَا تَابَ الْمُضِلُّونَ (48)

And you ‘An-Nabi ρ’ could not read any writing ‘even’ before this ‘Al-Waḥī,’ nor did you inscribe one with your right hand. Then [i.e., otherwise] the falsifiers would have been suspicious (Al-Ankabūt: 48)

The illiterate in these Ayāt has more than one meaning: The first: is the one who does not read or write. The second: He who does not have a heavenly book such as At-Torah and Al-Injil.

Ayāt	"هُوَ الَّذِي بَعَثَ فِي الْأُمِّيِّينَ رَسُولًا مِّنْهُمْ يَتْلُو عَلَيْهِمْ آيَاتِهِ وَيُزَكِّيهِمْ وَيُعَلِّمُهُمُ الْكِتَابَ وَالْحِكْمَةَ" (الجمعة- 2) سورة 62
Saḥīḥ	It is He who has sent among the unlettered a Messenger from themselves reciting to them His verses and purifying them and teaching them the Book and wisdom -
Shakir	He it is Who raised among the inhabitants of Mecca a Messenger from among themselves, who recites to them His communications and purifies them, and teaches them the Book and the Wisdom,
Yusuf 'Alī	It is He Who has sent amongst the Unlettered a messenger from among themselves, to rehearse to them His Signs, to sanctify them, and to instruct them in Scripture and Wisdom,-
M.Sarwar	It is He who has sent to the illiterate a Messenger from among their own people to recite to them His revelations and purify them. He will teach the Book to them.
Fahd Complex	He it is Who sent among the unlettered ones a Messenger (Muhammad SAW) from among themselves, reciting to them His Verses, purifying them (from the filth of disbelief and polytheism), and teaching them the Book (this Quran, Islamic laws and Islamic jurisprudence) and Al-Hikmah (As-Sunnah: legal ways, orders, acts of worship, etc. of Prophet Muhammad SAW).
Pickthall	He it is Who hath sent among the unlettered ones a messenger of their own, to recite unto them His revelations and to make them grow, and to teach them the Scripture and wisdom,
Arberry	It is He who has raised up from among the common people a Messenger from among them, to recite His signs to them and to purify them, and to teach them the Book and the Wisdom,
The Clear Qur'ān	He is the One Who raised for the illiterate 'people' a messenger from among themselves—reciting to them His revelations, purifying them, and teaching them the Book and wisdom,
Al-Minhaj	Saḥīḥ, Yusuf 'Alī, Moḥsin Fahd Complex, and Pickthall use the word "unlettered" for "الأميين," while Arberry uses "the common people," and Shakir uses "the inhabitants of Mecca" for it and uses "communications" instead of "Ayāt. Clear Qur'ān is the best to not to use "it" to refer to Allah ﷻ. They use the illiterate 'people' for "الأميين." Sarwar does not give tarjama for the word "Ḥikma." Fahd Complex is successful to give this Tafsīr: "the Book (this Quran, Islamic laws and Islamic jurisprudence) and Al-Hikmah (As-Sunnah: legal ways, orders, acts of worship, etc. of Prophet Muhammad SAW)." As seen earlier the dangerous role of deniers of as-Sunnah. This Tafsīr is very important in arguing with them. Minhaj recommends: "He is the One Who emitted for the illiterate..."

Conclusion

This study proves that Tarjamāt Ma'ānī (the meanings of) Al-Qur'ān Al-Karīm (TMQK), as one of the thorny issues, is to be considered one of 'Ulūm Al-QK, that needs to be fully theorised from an Islamic perspective. Depending on the fact that Al-QK is uniquely different from any other heavenly book, the study presents

its Minhaj al-Fiqh at-Tarjamī of Ma’ānī Al-QK as also unique and incomparable to any non-Islamic methods or approaches. The study criticizes the control of the Qur’ānic studies by anti-Islam movements that started their flawed theorization of TMQK during the Crusades, till its adoption by modern deviated movements and groups. Much of translation theory has been written from a Western perspective based on Classical Greek and Latin and from Biblical practice.

This study thus provides a foundation for additional research into the various elements of the criteria and responsibilities of a reliable turjumān of MQK. It calls for more sustained engagements among Muslim ‘ulama’ and researchers all over the world, in every available academic and non-academic institutions which are connected to ‘Ulūm al-Islam, widening the space for more proper reliable Ijazāt/ scholarships under this topic. This study paves the way for more thorough engagements that can develop more extensive activities beyond the scope of this study.

Endnotes

Key to Terms and Abbreviations

Symbol	Meanings
Y	Allah Almighty
ρ	Peace be upon him
τ	May Allah Be pleased with them
Terms/Abbr.	Meanings
Al-‘Arabiyya	Arabic language
Al-‘Arab (pl)	The Arab
Al-QK	Al-Qur’ān Al-Karīm
Dīn	Religion of Islam
Ijmā’	Islamic consensus
‘Ilm	Islamic science
Minhaj	The methodology
MQK	Ma’ānī/ Meanings of Al-Qur’ān Al-Karīm
Nabi	The Prophet in Islam
Rasūl	Messenger
Sīrah	As-Sīrah an-Nabawiyya (The biography of An-Nabi ρ)
Sunnah	As-Sunnah An-Nabawiyya Ash-Sharīfa
Tarjama/ Tarjamāt (pl)	Translation/s from an Islamic perspective Tarjamet (genitive) “translation of”
TMQK	Tarjamāt Ma’ānī Al-Qur’ān Al-Karīm
Turjumān/ Mutarjim	Plural: Mutarjimūn/in or Turjumans “translator/s”
Tandhīr	Islamic Theorisation
‘Ulamā’	Muslim Scholars
‘Ulūm	Plural of ‘Ilm

Transcription of 'Arabic Sounds

Symbol	Description	Examples
/ʔ/	ء	Voiceless glottal stop l'jāz/ "miraculousness"
/ħ/	ح	Voiceless pharyngeal fricative /ħarb/ "war"
/z/	ذ	Voiced dental fricative /zahab/ "gold"
/s/	ص	Voiceless alveolar emphatic fricative /şawm/ "fasting"
/d/	ض	voiced post-dental emphatic stop /maraḍ/ "sickness"
/t/	ط	Voiceless alveolar emphatic stop /maṭar/ "rain"
/ḏh/	ظ	voiced post-interdental emphatic fricative /ḏhahr/ "back"
/ʕa/	ع	Voiced pharyngeal fricative /ʕaql/ "mind"
/gh/	غ	Voiced uvular fricative / ghawth/ "help or aid"
Vowels		
/ī/		High front unrounded long vowel /karīh/ "hateful"
/ā/		Low central unrounded long vowel /qiṭār/ "train"
/ū/		High back round long vowel /nūr/ "light"

Note: Gemination is referred to by doubling the consonant

Ghalī's Towards Understanding the Ever-Glorious Qur'ān (4th ed.) is used as a guideline.

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يمثل هذا الكتاب الإصدار العلمي الرسمي للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر لبحوث اللغة والأدب والثقافة، الذي عُقد في أطلاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من جمعية سايبيلدر وبالشراكة مع عدد من الجامعات والمؤسسات الأكاديمية في تركيا وتونس ودول أخرى. ويضم هذا العمل مجموعة منتقاة من الأبحاث المحكمة التي اجتازت مراحل المراجعة العلمية وفق معايير الجودة والأمانة الأكاديمية.

تعكس الدراسات الواردة في هذا المجلد التنوع المعرفي والغنى المنهجي في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة، كما تبرز قيمة التعاون العلمي الدولي من خلال مشاركة باحثين من ثلاث عشرة دولة. ويؤكد هذا الإصدار أهمية دعم الحراك البحثي متعدد التخصصات وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي بلغات مختلفة بما يعزز حضور المعرفة في فضاء البحث العالمي.

وإذ نقدّم هذا الكتاب إلى المجتمع الأكاديمي، نعبّر عن تقديرنا للجهات الداعمة والهيئات العلمية والمحكمين والباحثين المشاركين، آمليين أن يسهم هذا العمل في تعزيز الدراسات ذات الصلة وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي المستدام.

ISBN: 978-625-92747-0-6

